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MS1 Initial Phase of Stakeholder Mapping & Next Steps

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BMD MS1 Initial Phase of Stakeholder Mapping & Next Steps

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Summary: A systematic, deliberative and iterative approach to identifying and mapping potential project stakeholders

This document outlines a systematic, deliberative and iterative approach to guide the stakeholder mapping activities for the Biodiversity Meets Data project. The approach is made up of six broad steps including: Define, Identify, Rate, Discuss, Categorise and Snowballing. The scope and rationale for engaging stakeholders in the project are reflected on, as defined by the project grant agreement. The findings from the initial phase of stakeholder mapping (MS1) are illustrated. The initial phase of stakeholder mapping created a preliminary longlist of relevant stakeholders based on the Eurosite network of natural site managers and conservation practitioners. Broad analysis of representation across European geographies and organisation types was carried out to identify emerging gaps and biases in stakeholder representation. The final section of the document includes a description of the next steps in the ongoing stakeholder mapping work that will contribute to the delivery of a detailed stakeholder database with relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to support the long term evaluation of gaps, biases and representation in the BMD stakeholder community throughout the course of the project.

List of Abbreviations

BMD	Biodiversity Meets Data
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SEP	Stakeholder Engagement Plan

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1. Introduction

Stakeholder mapping is the process by which relevant parties are identified, categorised, prioritised and selected for participation in an activity or project. Stakeholder mapping also allows for the identification of any biases and/or gaps in representation that may be present in a list of potential stakeholders, thus allowing projects to make targeted efforts to engage underrepresented stakeholders where needed. There are a variety of approaches, frameworks and methodologies that can be applied to achieve stakeholder mapping. For the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project the findings from the stakeholder mapping form the basis for the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) and future engagement activities that will occur throughout the course of the project. It is therefore important to apply an overall approach that is clearly defined (systematic), encourages active participation in decision-making (deliberative) and is adaptable to changing contexts, needs and knowledge (iterative).

This document begins by providing an overview of the stakeholder mapping process that will be applied in the BMD project. The scope and rationale for engaging stakeholders will be reflected on here, as defined by the grant agreement. The findings from the initial phase of stakeholder mapping will then be described (MS1.1) followed by a brief explanation of the next steps that will be taken in the ongoing stakeholder mapping work to be carried out in parallel with the development of the SEP.

2. Stakeholder Mapping Approach

Figure 1: Stakeholder Mapping Process Overview (adaptation of Reed et al. (2025) “3i” framework)

The stakeholder mapping approach outlined here is adapted from the Reed et al. (2025) “3i” framework for “analysing who is relevant to engage in environmental decision-making”. The 3i framework details a five-step process that prioritises active deliberation, transparency in decision-making and the consistent application of a clearly defined methodology. The five steps are as follows: define, identify, rate, discuss, and categorise (see Figure 1). In addition to this framework, related principles from the fields of design thinking, stakeholder engagement, participatory research and adaptive management have usefully informed the design of a stakeholder mapping process that is tailored to the specific context and needs of the BMD project. Taking into consideration the duration of the project (4 years), the large number of potential stakeholders, their varying levels of engagement in existing networks, and the likelihood of

varying capacities for participating in project activities, iterativity will be essential to the stakeholder mapping and implementation of engagement activities. With this in mind, “snowballing” has been added to the mapping framework as a sixth step that will occur throughout the lifecycle of the project. This will allow for the onboarding of stakeholders via workshops, events, online meetings and through the growing connections across the BMD consortium.

It is important to note that this mapping approach takes a high-level adaptation of the 3i framework for identifying relevant parties to engage. The 3i framework not only outlines a five-step process for identifying stakeholders, but also suggests a detailed approach to scoring and ranking stakeholders based on an influence-interest-impact matrix via a survey completed by researchers, and resulting in a 3i score for each individual stakeholder listed in the earlier stages of the mapping process (this scoring occurs in the “rate” stage of the mapping, see Reed et al. 2025). As the BMD project has already identified a large pan-European stakeholder community to engage in the project, it may not be practically feasible to apply the 3i methodology for scoring stakeholders. With this in mind, the approach outlined here ensures flexibility to allow the project team to determine the most effective and efficient approach to categorising stakeholders based on the criteria outlined in the grant agreement, and findings that emerge from deliberation and earlier mapping activities. Table 1 gives further details on the systematic, deliberative and iterative stakeholder mapping approach that will be applied in the BMD project. The underlying aims of the stakeholder mapping process described in Table 1 are to:

- Outline a clear approach to mapping that will inform the production of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan and guide the inclusion of stakeholders in project activities.
- Ensure that the decisions made regarding the inclusion of stakeholders in the project are based on deliberation and consensus building within the project team, fostering a culture of participation that can be applied to internal and external engagement processes.
- Take a systematic, deliberative and iterative approach to the stakeholder mapping process, utilising the expertise, networks and feedback from all teams in the BMD project.
- Highlight the necessary and appropriate steps to move from the identification of a longlist of relevant parties, to a consolidated and segmented list of Tier 1 and Tier 2 stakeholders.
- Produce a stakeholder typology and stakeholder database that can be used for monitoring, evaluating and tracking (via KPI’s) the stakeholder engagement process.
- Regularly analyse the representation, biases and gaps that may exist in the stakeholder database to form a baseline understanding of the composition of the BMD stakeholder community. This will allow us to track any changes as the stakeholder community grows over the course of the project. The baseline understanding that is produced from the mapping process, and the changes made visible via KPIs will allow us to make targeted efforts where appropriate to increase the representation of marginalised and underrepresented voices within the stakeholder community.

Table 1: Stakeholder Mapping Process in Detail (adaptation of Reed et al. (2025) “3i” framework)

Stage in Reed et al. (2025) framework	Stage in BMD Mapping Process	Description	Proposed Method
Define	Scope & Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline scope of project to make clear the initial broad range of stakeholders to consider (i.e. in project grant agreement). This will outline a broad set of inclusion and exclusion criteria for relevant parties (i.e. Europe; Natura 2000 site managers; policy representatives; marine, terrestrial and freshwater realms) Outline rationale for engaging stakeholders in project (i.e. in project grant agreement, co-design of SAP/VREs with regular stakeholder feedback and input) 	Project Grant Agreement Mapping notebook/log
Identify	Longlist 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Produce initial longlist of potential stakeholders based on researcher expertise and relevant networks (i.e. longlist based on Eurosite contacts) 	Excel database
	Analysis 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Broad analysis of representation and biases present in initial longlist to identify gaps (based on representation across geographies, organisation type and ecological realms) 	Table in Excel database Infographic
	Longlist 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add to the longlist based on wider project contacts, networks and suggestions 	Excel database
	Analysis 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Broad analysis of representation and biases present in v2 of the longlist to identify gaps (based on representation across geographies, organisation type and ecological realms) 	Table in Excel database Infographic

Rate	Develop Typology/Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agree on a set of criteria for the categorisation of listed relevant parties in order to develop a comprehensive and multidimensional typology of stakeholders relevant to the BMD project. Based on project grant agreement and a facilitated deliberative workshop/discussion in the WP1 team ● Elaborate on criteria for T1/T2 categories and any other criteria/categories for relevant parties (e.g. influence, interest, impact, level of engagement, channel of engagement etc.) 	<p>Internal workshop/discussion</p> <p>Mapping notebook/log</p>
	Apply Typology / Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Add columns to Excel database according to the criteria and typology agreed in previous stage ● For each stakeholder assign relevant score/attribute in each column according to criteria (e.g. high-interest, high-influence etc.) 	<p>Excel database</p> <p>Internal workshop / discussion or survey</p>
	Clustering & Segmentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assign a T1 or T2 category for each stakeholder based on these criteria in previous step (e.g. interest, influence, impact etc.) ● Broad analysis of representation and biases in these groups to help with refining and balancing the groups in next step (based on geography, organisation type and realm) 	<p>Excel database</p> <p>Internal workshop / discussion or survey</p>
Discuss	Discuss & agree grouping of stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Following clustering & segmentation, it is likely that the T1 group has a list of proposed stakeholders that is much larger than feasible (>10-15). Discuss the grouping of stakeholders in T1/T2 lists and refine to appropriate size 	<p>Excel Database</p> <p>Internal workshop / discussion</p>
Categorise	Agree final categories and prioritisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consensus on T1/T2 lists agreed within WP1 team 	<p>Excel Database</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Note any gaps or biases in representation to inform future targeted engagement strategies Propose set of stakeholder specific KPIs based on typology criteria (e.g. geography, organisation type, realms, desired level of engagement, current level of engagement etc.) 	Mapping notebook/log
Snowballing (additional step based on BMD grant agreement)	Add to stakeholder mapping database over course of project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add to the stakeholder database, based on new connections and suggestions from BMD consortium and participating stakeholders (tracked by ensuring a 'date added (m/Y)' column) Ensure typology and T1/T2 categorisation is applied to all new additions to database 	Excel Database Mapping notebook/log

3. Initial Phase of Stakeholder Mapping

The initial phase of stakeholder mapping involved defining the scope and rationale for engaging stakeholders and undergoing the first round of longlisting and analysis (see Figure 1 and Table 1). The scope (who to engage) and rationale (why) for engaging stakeholders in the BMD project were defined by the project grant agreement. The project grant agreement clearly states that “for maximum impact the project is co-designed with stakeholders, embedding their active participation throughout the project lifecycle” (BMD Project, 2024, p. 21). Table 2 further describes the scope and rationale for engaging stakeholders as defined by the project grant agreement, and this provides the initial boundaries for determining who to engage in the project.

Table 2: Scope and Rationale (BMD Project, 2024, pp. 21-22)

Scope	<p>The project will engage stakeholders with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “direct requirement to meet (inter)national obligations under the European regulatory framework, including the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Nature Directives, and including Natura 2000 reporting (SACs, SPAs and Emerald Network sites)” “direct and immediate responsibilities for protected site management”
Rationale	<p>The project seeks to generate impact for stakeholders and incorporate stakeholder participation and insights throughout its lifecycle. The</p>

	<p>rationale for engaging stakeholders is underpinned by the following priorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">(i) “stakeholders actively contribute from the design to delivery”(ii) “the project’s main outcomes fulfil the needs and expectations of communities of practice and wider groups of interest”
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3.1. Longlisting Phase 1

An initial longlist of potential stakeholders was produced based on the existing network of Eurosite members. The Eurosite network is a “community of natural site managers and conservation practitioners” (Eurosite, 2025), making this network particularly relevant as a starting point for identifying potential stakeholders to engage in the BMD project. Additionally, as Eurosite is a partner within the BMD Consortium, this network of stakeholders has an existing and trusted point of contact within the BMD project to enable future voluntary engagement activities. The purpose of this initial phase of longlisting was to produce a preliminary broad list of relevant and potentially interested stakeholders located across European biogeographies. Colleagues in the Work Package 1 team worked together to compile the longlist in an initial stakeholder database (using Excel), made a record of all Eurosite members in this database and assigned the relevant attributes to each record within the following broad categories:

- Name
- Organisation (or Occupation)
- Type of Organisation (Governmental, Research/Institute, NGO, Private (Business), Private (Individual))
- Country
- Email (if available)
- Website (if available)

3.2. Analysis Phase 1

Following the creation of a preliminary list of stakeholders in the first phase of longlisting, the Work Package 1 team performed analysis of the broad categories available in the stakeholder database. Basic visualisations were produced to illustrate the distribution of stakeholders across organisation types (see Figure 2) and European geographies (see Figure 3), as well as to highlight where any biases in representation may have already emerged (see Figure 4). An infographic was also produced using these visualisations, to reflect on the findings from the initial phase of stakeholder mapping and detailing the next steps in the mapping process.

The first phase of longlisting produced a list of 106 stakeholders located across 26 countries in Europe. Of these 106 stakeholders, the largest proportion were Private Individuals (29.2%), and the smallest proportion were Private Businesses (4.7%) (see Figure 2). Further analysis following iterative stakeholder mapping and deliberation will be required to understand what level of representation across

organisation types is appropriate and whether any of the categories are over/underrepresented in the database when compared with available data on natural resource managers and practitioners.

Figure 2: Percentage of Stakeholders across Organisation Type

As illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4, there is an emerging bias towards stakeholder representation in the North-Western countries in Europe, with South-Eastern Europe being underrepresented in the initial longlist. This is in part due to a large proportion of the longlisted stakeholders being located in the UK and the Netherlands. All other countries recorded in the longlist had six or fewer stakeholders listed, highlighting a significant gap in representation in the database. This indicates a need for another round of longlisting and future snowballing to further populate the stakeholder database and balance representation.

Figure 3: Distribution of Longlisted Stakeholders Across Europe

Figure 4: Relative Distribution of Longlisted Stakeholders across Europe (larger circles indicate a larger proportion of longlisted stakeholders located in labelled country)

4. Next Steps

The full approach outlined above will produce a detailed stakeholder typology and database, as well as a list of stakeholders grouped into Tier 1 and Tier 2 categories based on deployment of a systematic, deliberative and iterative mapping process. Additionally, a mapping notebook/log which records the process, methodology and decisions made during mapping, will be produced and will inform the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan. This notebook/log is for internal use only and acts as a research journal to ensure that methods, activities, decisions and reflections are captured and can be referred to at a later date where appropriate.

The stakeholder typology and database produced from the mapping process will provide a baseline for the monitoring and evaluation of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). For example, the representation of stakeholders across geographies, realms and organisation types will be recorded from the preliminary database, and at regular intervals (quarterly, as suggested in the project grant agreement), and when KPIs are reviewed any changes in this representation resulting from further snowballing will be recorded. This will be particularly important for guiding targeted efforts to engage marginalised and underrepresented stakeholders.

A summary of the outputs from the mapping process is as follows:

- Stakeholder Database with relevant KPIs (including an agreed list of Tier 1 & Tier 2 stakeholders)
- Stakeholder Typology
- Stakeholder Mapping Notebook/Logbook

The next steps following the reporting of the initial phase of stakeholder mapping (MS1):

- Outline a timeline for stakeholder mapping activities in parallel with the development of the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP deadline 31st July 2025)
- Incorporate feedback from BMD project council on overall mapping approach
- Coordinate an internal workshop to further define the stakeholder typology and relevant categories for stakeholder analysis and prioritisation (e.g. interest, influence, impact, biogeography, realm)

5. References

BMD Project (2024) BMD: Biodiversity Meets Data, Call: [Horizon-CL6-2024-BIODIV-01-2] – [Digital for Nature]

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